

LANGUAGE PORTFOLIOS IN THE ASSESSMENT OF STUDENTS IN LINGUODIDACTIC PROGRAMMES

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Abstract: This article explores the application of professional-oriented language portfolios in the interim assessment process of students in linguodidactic programs. Language portfolios serve as comprehensive tools for assessing students' language proficiency, pedagogical skills, and professional development. The study investigates the effectiveness of incorporating language portfolios in evaluating students' progress and the impact on their learning outcomes.

Keywords: Language portfolio, interim assessment, linguodidactic programs, language proficiency, pedagogical skills, professional development.

Since the beginning of the XXI century. More and more attention in the professionally oriented literature is paid to formative assessment, that is, assessment focused more on the development of knowledge, skills and abilities that form a test construct, rather than solely stating their level. One of the most common tools for such an assessment is the creation of a language portfolio. An example of such a portfolio is the "language portfolio" described in detail in pan-European documents.

In the pan-European documents of the 1990s concerning the use of the portfolio in teaching foreign languages, it is noted that its use is associated with the principle of lifelong learning. In a situation of professionally oriented assessment of communicative competence, it could also be added that the experience of creating and presenting a portfolio can also be useful to students in the context of future professional activities, in particular, elements of a portfolio or the entire portfolio can be used by them when passing an interview for a job. The very experience of creating and presenting such a document contributes to the development of not only communicative, but also existential competence of students, as it increases the level of awareness in their attitude to learning and to life in general. As for the experience of using a portfolio as an assessment tool, foreign scientists consider portfolio assessment, along with project activities, to be one of the main forms of "alternative" or formative assessment. The main difference between these types of assessment and standardized traditional tests is that by using alternative assessment tools, a wider range of evidence can be obtained that proves the achievement of curriculum goals. These proofs are presented in the form of work results, a

project, or a portfolio and can be archived and used later along with other evidence of learning as a compilation of evidence to demonstrate achievements. In the works of Russian scientists, the portfolio as an assessment tool attracted attention at the beginning of the XXI century, and has already been reflected in a large number of published works on pedagogy and methods of teaching foreign languages [3]. Within the framework of the report, the language portfolio will be considered not only as a formative tool, but also as a summative assessment. Recognizing the importance of portfolio creation experience for the development of professional and communication skills, we will focus on the potential of using this tool for summative intermediate assessment at the end of the year of study in language courses for special purposes. The professionally oriented specificity of this portfolio is due to the inclusion of works reflecting not only the level of communication, but also professional competencies, which allows students to use this portfolio in the future in the job search process. The presentation will present the portfolio structure, a test construct, criteria for evaluating professional and communicative competence based on a portfolio, as well as examples of portfolios created by students. The portfolio model used in the course includes four main parts. In the first part, students present a general report on their studies, where they describe what they managed to learn during the course, what they did better and worse, and what they see as the goals of further development for themselves in learning English and professional growth. In the second part, they cite the most significant resources that they have become familiar with during the course and give them a brief description.

In the third part, students analyze 5-7 works they created during the course and evaluate how these works demonstrate their strengths and weaknesses. Finally, as part of the last part of the portfolio, they are asked to evaluate on a one-hundred-point scale the level of increase in their professional knowledge, linguistic skills and professional, communicative and professional communication skills. As part of the oral part of the exam, students present a short portfolio presentation and answer the examiner's questions, justifying their choice of portfolio elements and the ideas that are presented in it on the basis of reflection.

It seems that this experience can be useful for possible implementation both in the framework of language courses for special purposes and practical foreign language courses at the level of higher education and subject-language integrated learning. In addition, the use of a portfolio can also be used for assessment at the turn of the bachelor's degree-master's degree as an

introductory assessment for admission to the master's degree, however, in this case it is worth noting that those students who have decided to change the direction of training and studied earlier in other training profiles, or did not have experience in creating a portfolio at the undergraduate level.

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